

Realising blue colour in cobalt substituted silicates: Synthesis, structure and optical studies[†]

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In an attempt to develop new blue coloured inorganic oxides, we have undertaken the cobalt substitution in Zn_2SiO_4 and $Ba_2ZnSi_2O_7$. In both the compounds, Zn occupies a tetrahedral coordination. Our studies indicate formation of single-phase materials only up to $x = 1.0$ in $Zn_{2-x}Co_xSiO_4$ and full replacement of Zn in $Ba_2Zn_{1-x}Co_xSi_2O_7$. The obtained compounds exhibit sky blue to intense blue colour, which appears to be stable in boiling water. The cobalt based blue compounds may be useful as new inorganic blue pigments.

Keywords: Inorganic pigments, chromophores, tetrahedral geometry, structure elucidation, solid-state structures.

Introduction

Coloured gemstones (Ruby, Sapphire etc.) have been of interest to mankind from ancient times. There are a number of naturally occurring minerals that are coloured and have been investigated for possible application as pigments¹. Over the years, many synthetic inorganic compounds exhibiting stable and bright colours have been explored as pigments²⁻⁴. The pigments, developed in recent years, have transition metal ions in different coordination environments and the colour arises due to the electronic transitions within the partially filled d-levels. Thus, green-coloured Y_2BaCuO_5 oxide⁵, blue-coloured $YIn_{1-x}Mn_xO_3$ oxides⁶, and oxides of different colours based on Co^{II} -, Ni^{II} -, and Cu^{II} -substituted $SrZnP_2O_7$ ⁷ appear to exhibit intense colour as well as pigment quality behaviour.

Of the many coloured compounds explored over the years, blue and red appears to be important. A number of blue coloured compounds have been prepared and reported in the literature^{6,8-12}. From the studies, it is clear that the presence of cobalt in tetrahedral coordination imparts intense blue colour. The compounds, $CaCu_3Si_4O_{12}$, Cuprorivaite¹³, and the Mn^{3+} substituted $YInO_3$ ⁶ are blue coloured compounds that do not have cobalt as part of the structure. It is known that the transition metal ions in solution have mostly

regular coordination geometries, in the solid state they exhibit unusual coordination as well as distorted geometries, which may be explored for new ligand field energies. This situation would likely result in giving rise to new colour for such compounds.

We have been interested in exploring coordination geometries of transition metal ions in different solid hosts and investigating the resulting colour^{14,15}. In continuation of this theme, we have now investigated Zn_2SiO_4 ¹⁶ and $Ba_2ZnSi_2O_7$ ¹⁷ as possible solid hosts for blue colour. Both the structures have Zn^{2+} ions in tetrahedral environment and provide scope for the exploration of blue colour by Co^{2+} substitution. Zn_2SiO_4 has been investigated as a luminescent host by substituting Zn^{2+} ions by Mn^{2+} ions, which results in yellow-green emission¹⁸. There have been studies of formation of the blue coloured compounds in Zn_2SiO_4 as well as $Ba_2ZnSi_2O_7$ ¹⁹. In the present study, we have undertaken a systematic investigation of the evolution of blue colour in both the compounds with the substitution of Co^{2+} for Zn^{2+} . The results are presented in the paper.

Experimental

Reagents: The chemicals, $BaCO_3$, ZnO , $CoC_2O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.9%), SiO_2 (Alfa Aesar 99%), were used as received.

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Synthesis: All the compounds were prepared employing a conventional ceramic method. Stoichiometric mixtures of BaCO_3 , ZnO , $\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, SiO_2 corresponding to the formula $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) and $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) were heated in air at 1050°C to 1200°C for 24 h with several intermittent grindings to obtain good quality crystal-line single phases.

Characterization: The prepared compounds were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). The PXRD patterns were recorded employing a Philips X'pert Diffractometer (Ni-filtered $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$, Ni-filter). The PXRD data for the Rietveld refinement of the structures were also collected at room temperature employing the same diffractometer in the 2θ range of $5\text{--}120^\circ$ (step size of 0.02° and duration 50 s). The PXRD patterns were refined using the program GSAS-EXPGUI²⁰. During the structure refinement, lattice parameters, scale factors, background (Fourier polynomial background function), pseudo-Voigt (U, V, W, and X), and isothermal temperature factors (U_{iso}) were refined. Thermal parameters were constrained to be the same for different atoms occupying the same sites. The PXRD patterns were simulated using POWDERCELL²¹ program employing the lattice positions reported in the literature¹⁰. The diffuse reflectance spectra for all the powdered samples were recorded by using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 UV/Vis double beam spectrometer over the spectral region of 250–1200 nm. The reflectance data were converted to the Kubelka-Munk²² function by using the equation,

$$F(R) = (1 - R)^2 / 2R = \alpha / S$$

in which R is the reflectance, α is absorptivity, and S is the scattering factor. The optical band gaps were obtained from the Tauc plots²³, employing the relation,

$$\alpha \cdot h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g)^n$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, A is a constant known as the band tailing parameter, n is the power factor of the transition mode. Plot of $(\alpha \cdot h\nu)^{1/n}$ versus the photon energy ($h\nu$) gives a straight line in a certain region. The extrapolation of the straight line intercepts the ($h\nu$)-axis which is taken as the optical band gap (E_g). NIR reflectance in the $\lambda = 500\text{--}2500 \text{ nm}$ range at RT were also collected. For characterization of the colour quality in the prepared compounds, the CIE 1931 chromaticity coordinates in the $\lambda = 380\text{--}750 \text{ nm}$ range and NIR reflectance in the $\lambda = 500\text{--}2500 \text{ nm}$ range

at RT were collected. The CIE 1931 chromaticity coordinates were determined by using the gocie.exe program²⁴.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and structure:

The crystal structure of Willemite, Zn_2SiO_4 , has a three-dimensional (3D) structure formed by the corner-sharing of tetrahedra. Thus, each SiO_4 tetrahedra are connected to two ZnO_4 tetrahedra forming the 3D structure (Fig. 1). The PXRD patterns of the prepared compounds indicated the formation of single-phase compounds iso structural to the parent Zn_2SiO_4 structure (Fig. 2). Our studies indicated that the sub-

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of Zn_2SiO_4 .

Fig. 2. PXRD patterns of $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$).

Table 1. Crystallographic parameters for ZnCoSiO₄ obtained from Rietveld refinement of the PXRD data

Atom	Site	x	y	z	$U_{\text{iso}} (\text{\AA}^{-2})$	Occupancy
Si	18f	0.979380	0.186230	0.772669	0.05712	1.0
Zn1/Co1	18f	0.982482	0.193404	0.414521	0.03332	0.5/0.5
Zn2/Co2	18f	0.981056	0.192998	0.083732	0.01624	0.5/0.5
O1	18f	0.094638	0.214689	0.773288	0.035906	1.0
O2	18f	-0.007378	0.304709	0.753825	0.005080	1.0
O3	18f	0.918109	0.124922	0.891760	0.019931	1.0
O4	18f	0.926123	0.132534	0.610779	0.027640	1.0

Space group *R*-3: $a = 13.962(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.328(1) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 120^\circ$.

Reliability factors: $R_p = 1.53\%$, $R_{wp} = 2.76\%$, $\chi^2 = 5.14$.

Bond lengths (\AA): Zn1/Co1-O = 1.989(2), Zn2/Co2-O = 2.072(1), Si-O = 1.57.

stitution of higher concentrations of cobalt in place of zinc in this structure ($x > 1.0$) leads to the formation of phase-segregated Zn₂SiO₄ (*R*-3) and Co₂SiO₄ (*Pbnm*) compounds (Fig. S1). Our studies clearly indicated that the solubility limits of Co²⁺ ion in Zn₂SiO₄ structure is $x \leq 1.0$.

We carried out Rietveld refinement for the end members, viz. Zn₂SiO₄ and Co₂SiO₄ (Fig. 3, S2 and Table 1). The

Fig. 3. Rietveld refinement of the PXRD data of ZnCoSiO₄. The observed (o), calculated (red lines), and difference (blue line) profiles are shown. The vertical bars indicate Bragg reflections.

Rietveld refinement study indicates that all the Zn_{2-x}Co_xSiO₄ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members crystallize in the Zn₂SiO₄ structure. From the refinements, it is clear that both Zn/Co ions occupy the same crystallographic position. We observed Zn/Co and Si are all coordinated by four O atoms forming the expected tetrahedral geometry with an average bond distance of 2.03 \AA and 1.57 \AA , respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Crystal structure of ZnCoSiO₄ (based on Zn₂SiO₄) drawn from the Rietveld refinement data.

$\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$):

The crystal structure of Ba₂ZnSi₂O₇ consists of ZnO₄ groups sharing oxygen atoms with the oxygen atoms of Si₂O₇ groups forming two-dimensional sheets. The Ba atoms are 8-coordinated and occupy spaces in between the sheets and connect the sheets to form three dimensional structure (Fig. 5). The PXRD studies indicated that entire solid solution in Ba₂Zn_{1-x}Co_xSi₂O₇ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) can be prepared as the crystalline single phasic material (Fig. 6).

The structure refinement of the end members, Ba₂ZnSi₂O₇ and Ba₂CoSi₂O₇ using Rietveld method was carried out (Fig. 7, S3 and Table 2). The Rietveld refinement also indicated that Ba₂Zn_{1-x}Co_xSi₂O₇ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members crystallize in the Ba₂ZnSi₂O₇ structure. From the refinements, we observed that the barium atoms have eight oxygen neighbours with an average Ba-O bond distance of 2.813 \AA ;

Fig. 5. Crystal structure of Ba₂ZnSi₂O₇.

Fig. 7. Rietveld refinement of the PXRD data of Ba₂CoSi₂O₇. The observed (o), calculated (red lines), and difference (blue line) profiles are shown. The vertical bars indicate Bragg reflections.

Fig. 6. PXRD patterns of Ba₂Zn_{1-x}Co_xSi₂O₇ (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.0).

the Zn-O distance of 1.96 Å; and the Si-O distances of 1.63 Å (Fig. 8). All of observed distances are in good agreement with the corresponding distances reported earlier²⁴.

Optical absorption studies:

The aim of the present study was to explore the evolution of the blue colour in the compounds. As part of the studies, we have presently explored two series of compounds: Zn_{2-x}Co_xSiO₄ (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.0) and Ba₂Zn_{1-x}Co_xSi₂O₇ (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.0) compounds.

Zn_{2-x}Co_xSiO₄ (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.0):

The parent compound, Zn₂SiO₄, is white in colour with a

Table 2. Crystallographic parameters for Ba₂CoSi₂O₇ obtained from Rietveld refinement of the PXRD data

Atom	Site	x	y	z	U _{iso} (Å ⁻²)	Occupancy
Ba	8f	0.274728	0.458011	0.024796	0.025796	1.0
Co	4e	0.0	0.258030	0.250000	0.008948	1.0
Si	8f	0.883732	0.286755	0.858891	0.016050	1.0
O1	4e	0.0	0.328828	0.75	0.053889	1.0
O2	8f	0.700966	0.335390	0.773933	0.067531	1.0
O3	8f	0.972786	0.350456	0.048209	0.032223	1.0
O4	8f	0.886933	0.139643	0.859131	0.016312	1.0

Space group C2/c: a = 8.449(2) Å, b = 10.725(2) Å, c = 8.469(1) Å, α = γ = 90°, β = 111.365°.

Reliability factors: R_p = 2.60%, R_{wp} = 3.12%, χ² = 2.48.

Bond lengths (Å): Ba-O = 2.851(2), Co-O = 1.917(2), Si-O = 1.60.

Fig. 8. Crystal structure of $\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$ drawn from the Rietveld refinement data.

Fig. 9. Colors of the $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members in daylight.

Fig. 10. Optical absorption (UV/Vis) spectra of $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members.

band gap (E_g) of ~ 5.2 eV. On substitution of Zn^{2+} ions with Co^{2+} ions in $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$, the colour changes progressively

from sky blue to intense blue with increasing value of x (Fig. 9). The optical absorption spectra (Fig. 10) of $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) exhibit a broad triplet absorption band in the range 1.75 to 2.70 eV (710 to 460 nm) with a maximum at 2.0 eV. The strong absorption observed around 2.0 eV is in the orange-red region and the complementary colour would be blue. There are three transitions known for the tetrahedral cobalt and correspond to the (i) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_2(F)$ (~ 0.5 eV), (ii) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ (0.6 to 1.25 eV) and (iii) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ (1.6 to 2.7 eV) transitions^{8, 25-27}. The two spin-allowed transitions (i) and (ii) are in the IR region whereas the third spin-allowed transition, [${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$] is in the visible region. Accordingly, the triplet band centered around 2.0 eV can be assigned to the tetrahedral Co^{II} (d^7): ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition. Similar transitions involving cobalt(II) in tetrahedral coordination has been observed in other oxides^{9,10}.

The parent compound, $\text{Ba}_2\text{ZnSi}_2\text{O}_7$, is also white in colour with a band gap (E_g) of ~ 5.0 eV. On substitution of Co^{2+} in place of Zn^{2+} , the Co-substituted compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) exhibit a gradual change from light blue to dark blue under daylight (Fig. 11). Similar to the

Fig. 11. Colors of the $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members in daylight.

$\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ compounds, the optical absorption spectra (Fig. 12) exhibits a broad triplet absorption band in the range 1.7 to 2.7 eV (710 to 460 nm) with a maximum at 2.0 eV. The strong absorption observed at 2.0 eV is in the orange-red region and the complementary colour would be in the blue region. Thus, under daylight the prepared compounds do exhibit intense blue colour. There are three spin-allowed transitions known for tetrahedral Co^{II} (d^7): (i) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_2(F)$, (ii) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ and (iii) ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ ^{8,25-27}. The first two are the spin-allowed transitions that lie in the IR

Fig. 12. Optical absorption (UV/Vis) spectra of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members.

region, whereas the third spin-allowed transition [$^4A_2(F) \rightarrow ^4T_1(P)$] falls in the visible region. Thus, we assigned the triplet band centered around 2.00 eV to the tetrahedral Co^{II} (d^7): $^4A_2(F) \rightarrow ^4T_1(P)$ transition.

NIR reflectance spectra:

TiO_2 is white in colour and also known to have a strong near-IR reflectance²⁸. The white-coloured parent compounds, Zn_2SiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{ZnSi}_2\text{O}_7$ were examined for near IR-reflectance. The studies indicate that near-IR reflectivity of ~80% (Fig. 13), which is better than the near-IR reflectivity observed

Fig. 13. Comparison of UV/Vis and NIR reflectance (%) of Zn_2SiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{ZnSi}_2\text{O}_7$ with TiO_2 .

for TiO_2 (~70%). It is likely that the white compounds could be candidates to act as white pigments with high near-IR reflectivity.

In order to quantify the colour of the prepared compounds, we determined the CIE 1931 chromaticity coordinates for the cobalt substituted ZnCoSiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$ (Figs. 14, 15, Tables S3, S4). The chromaticity results clearly corre-

Fig. 14. CIE chromaticity diagrams for the $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members.

Fig. 15. CIE chromaticity diagrams for the $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$) members.

spond to the blue region for ZnCoSiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$. The colour coordinates (L^* , a^* and b^* parameters) for the blue-coloured compounds were compared with other blue coloured compounds known in the literature such as CoAl_2O_4 ⁹ and $\text{YIn}_{0.9}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ ⁹ (Table 3). The present compounds appear to be comparable with the reported blue-coloured compounds.

Table 3. Color coordinates for ZnCoSiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$, CoAl_2O_4 and $\text{YIn}_{0.9}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$

Compound	L^*	a^*	b^*
ZnCoSiO_4	9.45	15.56	-78.52
$\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$	33.42	6.25	-61.56
CoAl_2O_4 ^a	44.80	2.10	-32.70
$\text{YIn}_{0.9}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ ^a	39.71	-5.78	-22.28

^aData for CoAl_2O_4 , $\text{YIn}_{0.9}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$, were taken from Ref. [9].

We have also carried out a colour stability test for both the ZnCoSiO_4 and $\text{Ba}_2\text{CoSi}_2\text{O}_7$ compounds by keeping the solids in hot (boiling) water for 24 h. After this hot water treatment, the samples were filtered and dried and examined employing PXRD and UV/Vis spectroscopic studies, which indicated clearly that the compounds are stable and exhibit identical PXRD patterns and UV/Vis spectra (Figs. S4-S9).

Conclusions

We have undertaken a systematic study of the evolution of blue colour in $\text{Zn}_{2-x}\text{Co}_x\text{SiO}_4$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$), $\text{Ba}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1.0$). From the PXRD studies, it is established that the cobalt substitution in place of Zn is Zn_2SiO_4 is limited to $x = 1.0$. The optical absorption spectra of the compounds were interpreted on the basis of ligand-field transitions that occurred within the distorted tetrahedral Zn/CoO₄ chromophores. The parent compounds exhibit good near-IR reflectivity. The CIE coordinates as well as stability studies indicate that the present Co-substituted blue compounds could act as good blue pigments.

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References

1. P. Ball, "Bright Earth: Art and the Invention of Colour", The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 2001.
2. "Industrial Inorganic Pigments", ed. G. Buxbaum, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 1998.
3. H. Berke, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2007, **36**, 15.
4. M. Jansen and H. P. Letschert, *Nature*, 2000, **404**, 980.
5. J. K. Kar, R. Stevens and C. R. Bowen, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2008, **455**, 121.
6. A. E. Smith, H. Mizoguchi, K. Delaney, N. A. Spaldin, A. W. Sleight and M. A. Subramanian, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 17084.
7. A. E. I. Jazouli, B. Thib, A. Demourgues and M. Gaudon, *Dyes Pigm.*, 2014, **104**, 67.
8. M. Zayat and D. Levy, *Chem. Mater.*, 2000, **12**, 2763.
9. S. Tamilarasan, M. L. P. Reddy, S. Natarajan and J. Gopalakrishnan, *Chem. Asian J.*, 2016, **11**, 3234.
10. A. Bhim, S. Laha, J. Gopalakrishnan and S. Natarajan, *Chem. Asian J.*, 2017, **12**, 2734.
11. M. Gaudon, A. Apecheixborde, M. Menetrier, A. Le Nestour and A. Demourgues, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, **48**, 9085.
12. L. Robertson, M. Duttine, M. Gaudon and A. Demourgues, *Chem. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 2419.
13. Y. Chen Min, K. Sun and P. J. Jena, *Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2016, **7**, 399.
14. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 1968.
15. H. M. Smith, "High Performance Pigments", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2002.
16. K. H. Klaska, J. Eck and C. D. Pohl, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1978, **34**, 3324.
17. J. W. Kaiser and W. Jeitschko, *Z. Kristallogr. – New Cryst. Struct.*, 2002, **217**, 25.
18. C. Bertail, S. Maron, V. Buissette, T. Le Mercier, T. Gacoin and J.-P. Boilot, *Chem. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 2961.
19. R. D. Adams and R. Layland, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 3492.
20. A. C. Larson and R. B. Von Dreele, "General Structure Analysis System (GSAS)", Los Alamos National Laboratory Report LAUR, 2000, 86.
21. W. Kraus and G. Nolze, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1996, **29**, 301.
22. P. Kubelka and F. Munk, *Z. Tech. Phys.*, 1931, **12**, 593.
23. J. Tauc, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 1968, **3**, 37.
24. <https://code.google.com/archive/p/jtchem/downloads>.
25. G. Lorenzi, G. Baldia, F. D. Benedettob, V. Faso, P. Lattanzi and M. Romanelli, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2006, **26**, 317.

26. G. Costa, M. J. Ribeiro, W. Hajjaji, M. P. Seabra, J. A. Labrincha, M. Dondi and G. Cruciani, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, 2009, **29**, 2671.
27. M. Gaudon, L. C. Robertson, E. Lataste, M. Duttine, M. Menetrier and A. Demourgues, *Ceram. Int.*, 2014, **40**, 5201.
28. Y. Wang, J. Li, L. Wang, T. Qi, D. Chen and W. Wang, *Chem. Eng. Technol.*, 2011, **34**, 905.